

Smart Tape for Monitoring the Automated Tape Layering Process Using All-Grating Fiber Sensors

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ABSTRACT

In the context of the GENEX project, a procedure has been developed to monitor the Automated Tape Layering (ATL) process with an in-situ consolidation system using fiber optic sensors (FOS). A specialized type of optical fiber, All Grating Fiber (AGF), was employed. This fiber is densely engraved with Fiber Bragg Gratings (FBGs) along its entire length, functioning as a quasi-distributed sensor. The AGF fiber was embedded in composite Carbon Fiber (CF) tapes, which were pre-impregnated with a thermoplastic-like thermoset resin customized to a specific glass transition temperature (T_g). The embedding process occurred simultaneously with the resin impregnation. The AGF sensor monitors the ATL process by measuring the temperature during tape deposition and the force/pressure applied by the consolidation roller. This approach aims to optimize the ATL process window and ensure defect-free laminate consolidation.

Keywords: optical fiber sensors, fiber Bragg gratings, all grating fiber, embedded sensors, automated tape layering, fiber reinforced composites, composite manufacturing

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite material technology has gained relevance across different industries, particularly in the aerospace industries which benefit from the excellent ratio of light weight and stiffness for the structures of aircraft components, like fuselage panels or wing skins. It is due to the nature of composite materials, which are a combination of two base materials with different physical and chemical properties, being one of the components a polymeric matrix and the other a reinforcement consisting of fibers or filaments like glass or carbon. There are many different manufacturing techniques for composite materials like resin transfer molding (RTM), vacuum infusion or compression molding to name a few. Automated Tape Layering (ATL) is a type of additive manufacturing method to fabricate complex composite components, consisting in a layer-by-layer multi-directional placement of continuous tape. This tape is usually composed of unidirectional carbon fibers acting as the reinforcement, pre-impregnated in a thermoset or thermoplastic resin.

Fiber optic sensors (FOS) are a good option for monitoring fabrication processes because of their high sensitivity to temperature changes and strain, immunity to electromagnetic interference, multiplexing capabilities and their low-invasive embedment capabilities. The application of FOS in ATL processes is still underdeveloped due to challenges poses for the correct embedment of the FOS. The typical type of FOS employed are single FBGs, usually the gratings are positioned manually and glued to the layers of composite [1][2]. In the scope of GENEX EU Project [3], it was developed a monitorization system for ATL manufacturing consolidation process by FOS embedded during the carbon fiber (CF) tape resin impregnation manufacturing. The selected FOS was an All-Grating Fiber (AGF) from FBGS, a special type of optical fiber that is densely engraved along its length with spaced single Fiber Bragg Gratings (FBGs). The spatial separation from center to center is 10mm and it can have gratings along more than 95% of the fiber. The whole system works as a distributed FOS measuring the reflections of the gratings at the different points of the fiber length. Thus, it is used for measuring strain or temperature with spatial resolution from 1.59mm over the entire fiber length.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE AND SETUP

The first step is to embed the fiber in the tape. It is made during the resin impregnation process of the tape. The resin is developed by CIDETEC. The selected material is a new 3R (recyclable, repairable and reprocessable) epoxy based vitrimer with a customized T_g. In Figure 1(a)(b) it is shown a series of photographs of the impregnation process and Figure 1(c) shows a detail of the fiber embedded within the tape. The AGF is loaded mutually with the CF tape and immersed in the 3R resin bath, in a continuous roll to roll Basecoater Coatema® machine.[3]

Figure 1: (a) Impregnation of the tape and the FOS, (b) comparison between the impregnated tape ready to be spooled and the uncoated one (Property of CIDETEC) (c) detail of the fiber embedded in the tape, illuminated by a red diode laser.

The tape is a commercial carbon fiber tape, Tenax® HTA40 400, with a density of 250 g/m², a width of 25mm and 6k filaments. The AGF is coated with Ormocer® from FBGS, with a cladding diameter of 125 μm and a coating of 195 μm. After a visual inspection of the tape to verify the embedment is properly done, the fiber is connectorized and the obtained sensorized pre-preg tape is then placed in the appropriate spool for the ATL. The embedded AGF in the tape is connected to the Summit interrogator from Sensuron through a rotary junction to escape the ATL spool rotation.

The robotic head of an ATL machine is depicted in the photographs below in Figure 2(a)(b). It consists of a spool holder, a tape guidance system, a compactation roller, a tape cutter and a laser as a heat source. The robotic head is programmed to make the trajectories to deposit the pre impregnated tapes in the desired orientation, then un-spools and loads the tape and places a stripe of tape, referred as ply, while simultaneously heating the resin and sliding the compactation roller (Figure 2(c)) over it consolidating the material. At the end of the deposition, the tape is cut by the blade integrated in the ATL head. In addition, it allows to select the laser power, deposition speed or consolidation roller pressure. Finally, after the composite laminate is manufactured by the ATL, it must be cured. To do so, is placed inside a vacuum bag in an oven at 180°C for at least 8 hours for the final curing of the polymeric resin.

Figure 2: (a)(b)(c) Photographs of the ATL machine, the system with the robotic arm and the details of the consolidating head, and the roller. (d) Schematic of the whole ATL + AGF monitoring system

3. RESULTS

In this section, the results of monitoring the manufacturing of a test laminate using pre-impregnated tape with embedded FOS are presented. The laminate (Laminate 1, L1) consisted of 4 plies stacked together, with a consolidated length of 320mm and a width of 25mm. It was fabricated using a laser power of 600W and a tape speed of 140-180mm/s.

Figure 3(a) shows a colormap representing the whole signal from the AGF collected during the manufacturing of the laminate. It is a representation of the variation of the AGF wavelength (color bar) along each point of the fiber (x-axis) through the process time (y-axis). The abrupt steps that are observed correspond to the moment when the taper ply is automatically cut by the ATL. Because of that, it is possible to identify precisely what region corresponds to each ply and analyze the deposition process for them. The deposition starts at the point furthest from the connector, in this case, around meter 7.5. With each deposition, the total length of the AGF sensor embedded in the tape on the spool is reduced.

Figure 3: (a) Complete signal from the Laminate 1 (L1) fabrication. The circles remark when the tape is cut at the end of each of 4 plies, in (b) the signal is zoomed to the final 2 s before the cut, where the information of the process is contained

The information of the ATL process is contained only in the last 2 seconds before the tape is cut. Therefore, when the interface at each step (marked with black circles in the graph of Figure 3) is zoomed until it is represented those 2 seconds, a characteristic oblique gradient can be observed, as shown in Figure 3(b). This gradient corresponds to the consolidated area of the tape for each ply and represents the variation of the AGF wavelength at the very instant of the tape consolidation, caused by the heat of the laser and the pressure of the roller.

In Figure 3(b), it can be observed that Ply 2 exhibits a higher wavelength variation compared to the others. This may be due to irregularities in the impregnation of the tape, causing an accumulation of resin in some areas, which could cause slight overheating during deposition. Ply 4 also presents an anomaly in the region between 5.5 and 5.4 meters, suggesting a slightly weaker consolidation in that zone. However, visual inspection of the laminate after fabrication did not reveal any perceptible defects. Figure 4(a) shows a photograph of the complete laminate, where the four plies are stacked, and the consolidation region is visible. The AGF is perfectly embedded, making it impossible to detach from the tape and even hard to see it entangled within the carbon fibers.

After curing, a sample of the laminate is transversely sliced from its center, then encapsulated, polished and examined under the microscope following a procedure similar to metallographic analysis. Figure 4(b) shows a microphotograph of the laminate sample. In this section, it can be corroborated that the AGF is properly embedded, with the fiber appearing as four lighter double concentric circles arranged diagonally. It can also be concluded that the laminate is well consolidated.

Figure 4: (a) Photograph of the laminate just manufactured, the central region is the consolidated part. (b) Microphotograph of the laminate section where the AGF is embedded.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This work demonstrates the successful integration of All Grating Fiber (AGF) sensors in Automated Tape Layering (ATL) processes for real-time monitoring. The AGF sensors, embedded in pre-impregnated carbon fiber tapes, provided information on temperature and pressure during the deposition and consolidation of the layers. The obtained data allowed the identification of irregularities in tape impregnation and consolidation, although no visible defects were observed in the laminate. The AGF fiber remained properly embedded, confirming its robust integration capability. Additionally, microstructural validation showed that the fiber was defect-free, demonstrating the reliability of the monitoring system. This methodology opens opportunities to optimize composite material manufacturing, improving the ATL process quality.

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